

A survey of rapid sequence induction (RSI) and intubation practice in paediatric patients

Tick the appropriate block

1. What grade of anaesthetist are you?

Medical officer	
Junior registrar (<2yrs)	
Senior registrar (>2yrs)	
Principal medical officer	
Consultant < 5 years	
Consultant 5 – 10 years	
Consultant >10 years	

2. For registrars only – How long ago did you complete your paediatric training block?

Have not yet done the block	
Currently doing the block	
0 - 12 months ago	
1 – 2 years ago	
> 2 years ago	

3. For consultants only – How often do you anaesthetise children?

At least one list per week	
At least one list per month	
Less than one list per month	
Never	

4. For which of the following cases would you use a RSI technique?
(You can choose more than one option)

Any emergency case	
A non-fasted patient	
An upper GIT obstruction	
A lower GIT obstruction	
Appendicitis with localized pain and soft abdomen	
Appendicitis with distended abdomen and generalized peritonitis	
A patient with bulbar palsy	
Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus	
Renal failure	

5. In your opinion, what are the **2** most important components of a *controlled* RSI?
(Choose 2)

Attempting laryngoscopy and intubation immediately after induction	
Maintaining oxygenation using appropriate bag-mask ventilation	
Waiting for the 'magical minute' before intubating the patient	
The use of cricoid pressure	
Ensuring adequate depth of anaesthesia and paralysis before intubation	

During a RSI for paediatric patients:

Key:

Neonate	< 28 days old
Infant	1 month-1 year
Child	1-12 years

1. Which is your preferred method of pre-oxygenation for

(A) a neonate:

Normal tidal breathing If so, for how long?		Do not attempt pre-oxygenation	
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(B) an infant:

Normal tidal breathing If so, for how long?		Do not attempt pre-oxygenation	
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(C) a child

Normal tidal breathing If so, for how long?		Vital capacity breaths. If so, how many?.....		Do not attempt pre-oxygenation	
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2. Which induction agent do you use in a haemodynamically stable patient for

(A) a neonate

Propofol		Ketamine		Etomidate		Sevoflurane		Other (specify)	
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(B) an infant

Propofol		Ketamine		Etomidate		Sevoflurane		Other (specify)	
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(C) a child

Propofol		Ketamine		Etomidate		Sevoflurane		Other (specify)	
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3. Which paralyzing agent do you use during induction for

(A) a neonate

Suxamethonium		Rocuronium		Cis-/atracurium		None		Other (specify)	
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(B) an infant

Suxamethonium		Rocuronium		Cis-/atracurium		None		Other (specify)	
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(C) a child

Suxamethonium		Rocuronium		Cis-/atracurium		None		Other (specify)	
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4. Do you use cricoid pressure in

(A) a neonate

YES		NO	
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(B) an infant

YES		NO	
-----	--	----	--

(C) a child

YES		NO	
-----	--	----	--

5. Do you use bag-mask-ventilation during a RSI in

(A) a neonate

YES		NO	
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(B) an infant

YES		NO	
-----	--	----	--

(C) a child

YES		NO	
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If so, what is your maximum inspiratory pressure used while bag-mask-ventilating the patient?

<12 cmH ₂ O	
12 – 16 cmH ₂ O	
>16 cmH ₂ O	

6. Do you use a nerve stimulator to monitor adequate paralysis prior to intubation?

YES		NO	
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7. Do you use ultrasound to assess the presence of gastric content prior to a RSI?

YES		NO	
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8. Do you routinely assess clinical parameters of volume-status prior to performing a RSI for a paediatric patient?

YES		NO	
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9. Do you use a cuffed or uncuffed endotracheal tube for a paediatric patient at risk of pulmonary aspiration in:

(A) a neonate

cuffed		uncuffed	
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(B) an infant

cuffed		uncuffed	
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(C) a child

cuffed		uncuffed	
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10. Would you find it useful to have guidelines which direct you on the conduct of RSI for paediatric patients?

YES		NO	
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Clinical Scenarios:

You are asked to anaesthetise the patient in the following scenarios:

Please describe the technique you would most commonly use to establish anaesthesia by indicating on the table, the components you would use and the order you would use them:

(1= first action, 2= second action, and so forth. You do not have to use all components)

- A 3-week-old, otherwise healthy baby, for a pyloromyotomy. He has been fully resuscitated with IV fluids but the cannula came out during transfer to OT. He has a nasogastric tube in-situ that appears to be draining well.**

Components	Use (Circle)	Sequence order (Circle)
Site intravenous access	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Insert/suction naso/orogastric tube	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Pre-oxygenation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Induction	Intravenous/ Inhalational	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Cricoid pressure	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Appropriate Bag-mask-ventilation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Muscle relaxant	<u>Circle drug of choice</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suxamethonium (Sux) • Rocuronium (Roc) • Cis-/Atracurium (Cis-Atr) • None (∅) 	Sux / Roc / Cis-Atr/ ∅	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Definitive airway control		N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laryngeal mask airway (LMA) • Cuffed endotracheal tube (cETT) • Uncuffed endotracheal tube (uETT) 	LMA / cETT / uETT	

2. A 4-year-old, previously healthy child who has suspected small bowel obstruction. He has been unwell for 48hrs, with episodes of vomiting and a tender, distended abdomen. He has an IV line running and has been resuscitated. There is no naso/orogastric tube in place.

Components	Use (Circle)	Sequence order (Circle)
Site intravenous access	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Insert/suction naso/orogastric tube	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Pre-oxygenation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Induction	Intravenous/ Inhalational	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Cricoid pressure	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Appropriate Bag-mask-ventilation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Muscle relaxant	<u>Circle drug of choice</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suxamethonium (Sux) • Rocuronium (Roc) • Cis-/Atracurium (Cis-Atr) • None (∅) 	Sux / Roc / Cis-Atr/ ∅	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Definitive airway control		N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laryngeal mask airway (LMA) • Cuffed endotracheal tube (cETT) • Uncuffed endotracheal tube (uETT) 	LMA / cETT / uETT	

3. A 6-year-old, otherwise healthy child who has a painful forearm fracture requiring manipulation. He ate 2hrs prior to the injury and has now been starved for 6hrs since the injury. He has received opioids in the pre-operative period.

Components	Use (Circle)	Sequence order (Circle)
Site intravenous access	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Insert/suction naso/orogastric tube	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Pre-oxygenation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Induction	Intravenous/ Inhalational	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Cricoid pressure	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Appropriate Bag-mask-ventilation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Muscle relaxant	<u>Circle drug of choice</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suxamethonium (Sux) • Rocuronium (Roc) • Cis-/Atracurium (Cis-Atr) • None (∅) 	Sux / Roc / Cis-Atr/ ∅	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Definitive airway control		N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laryngeal mask airway (LMA) • Cuffed endotracheal tube (cETT) • Uncuffed endotracheal tube (uETT) 	LMA / cETT / uETT	

4. A 7-year-old with renal failure and ascites who has been booked for Tenckhoff catheter insertion, in order to commence dialysis. It is an elective procedure and the child has been starved:

Components	Use (Circle)	Sequence order (Circle)
Site intravenous access	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Insert/suction naso/orogastric tube	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Pre-oxygenation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Induction	Intravenous/ Inhalational	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Cricoid pressure	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Appropriate Bag-mask-ventilation	Y / N	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Muscle relaxant	<u>Circle drug of choice</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suxamethonium (Sux) • Rocuronium (Roc) • Cis-/Atracurium (Cis-Atr) • None (∅) 	Sux / Roc / Cis-Atr/ ∅	N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
Definitive airway control		N/A 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laryngeal mask airway (LMA) • Cuffed endotracheal tube (cETT) • Uncuffed endotracheal tube (uETT) 	LMA / cETT / uETT	